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CASE STUDIES

The work presented on this site aims to gather and report on the technical details, business cases, and stakeholder stories associated with examples where data-driven solutions have been implemented in the real world. Each case study focuses on a particular building, technology, or dataset. Individually, the case study descriptions aspire to highlight a particular facet of applying data-driven smart building technologies. Collectively, the case studies help garner an understanding of the current state of practice and possibly help identify a path forward to critically understanding some of the benefits and challenges associated with data-driven smart buildings.

This page is a work-in-progress. In the coming two years, we will be updating the site with case studies contributed by Annex participants and their collaborators.

ZUB BUILDING

Germany

The ZUB office building (Center for Environmentally Consciou ...

[+ See Case Study](#)

LBNL "BUILDING 59" OFFICE BUILDING

United States

The LBNL Office Building (i.e., Building 59 or Wang Hall) is ...

[+ See Case Study](#)

OMV HEAD OFFICE BUILDING

Austria

The OMV headquarter is an existing building located in Viert ...

[+ See Case Study](#)

EV BUILDING, CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY

Canada

This building is in one of the city's main intersections (Sa ...

[+ See Case Study](#)

INFINEON RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT BUILDING

Austria

The building is a research and development building of Infin ...

[+ See Case Study](#)

CSIRO SYNERGY BUILDING

Australia

With every chilled plant being unique, human optimisation is ...

[+ See Case Study](#)

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ABOUT

Welcome to the International Energy Agency's (IEA) Annex 81 project on Data-driven Smart Buildings.

The work presented on this site gathers and reports on the technical details, business cases, and stakeholder stories associated with examples where data-driven solutions have been implemented in the real world. Each case study focuses on a particular building, technology, or dataset. The case studies presented here have been collected by Annex participants and reflect applications of smart building technologies from around the world.

Individually, the case study descriptions aspire to highlight a particular facet of applying data-driven smart building technologies. Each case study considers benefits and disbenefits, challenges related to applying such technologies, lessons learnt and unintended consequences. To understand the potential for adoption and success of any innovation, it is necessary to capture the relevant context. In this regard, we seek to understand the value proposition for the different stakeholders and how this can drive technological and business model innovation.

Collectively, the case studies help garner an understanding of the current state of practice and possibly help identify a path forward to critically understanding some of the benefits and challenges. It is common with technological innovations that hype usually raises expectations to unrealistic levels. While such hype might drive early adopters and researchers, actual adoption at scale is only possible when a clear value proposition exists and is demonstrated in practice. In this regard, we seek to collect knowledge from early adopters of such technologies and distil these so that the benefits can be understood by a wider audience and support evidence-based decision making or the development of relevant policies.

OVERVIEW OF ANNEX 81

IEA's Energy in Buildings and Communities programme supports IEA Annex 81 (Research Project) on "Data-driven Smart Buildings", which brings together more than 100 collaborators from 19 countries. This activity is part of IEA Annex 81 activities.

The overarching aim of Annex 81 is to increase access to low-cost, high-quality data from buildings and support the development of data-driven energy efficiency 'Applications' and analytics. This will: (i) enable automated energy efficiency optimisation of building operations and (ii) provide energy efficiency data and decision support for building facilities managers.

CONTEXT

The recent revolution in digital technology and cyber-physical systems has the potential to reduce costs and overcome barriers to energy efficiency through advanced control and operation of building HVAC systems. Emerging digital tools include

- The Internet of Things (IoT); provides access to more diverse, low-cost data on the status and activity of equipment and people in buildings.
- Artificial intelligence and data analytics; enable more comprehensive energy performance assessment and predictive management of assets.
- Sharing economy platforms; providing new business models for connecting users and energy efficiency software services providers.

Unfortunately, progress in the digitalisation of building services has been slow, and the application of digitalisation for improving energy efficiency in buildings has not reached its full potential. Open data concepts have been proposed to reduce barriers and stimulate innovation in energy efficiency software services.

This project imagines a future world empowered by access to low-cost information-rich data from buildings through an open data-exchange platform, enabling software 'Applications' (such as model-based control and fault detection and diagnosis (FDD)) to scale rapidly.

OBJECTIVES

Annex 81 strategy is to map the current technology and innovation landscape in non-domestic smart buildings and data-driven building services; we seek to collect information and provide inputs to support the definition of the tools developed within the Annex. Once these tools have been developed, activities within Annex 81 will seek to understand their performance and lessons learned and identify new service models. The knowledge generated will be communicated to relevant stakeholders such as academic, industry and government groups, and inputs will be fed back to the technical work of the Annex.

METHODOLOGY

This research aims to map the current technology and innovation landscape in non-domestic smart buildings and data-driven building services. In this context, we seek to collect qualitative and quantitative information from case study buildings to develop exemplar technical briefs summarising the technical details, business cases and stakeholder stories associated with implementing these technologies in the real world. We will compile technical briefs and quantitative datasets (if available) with the information collected and communicate to relevant stakeholders from academia, industry, and government groups to advance the current understanding of smart buildings and data-driven solutions.

We are particularly looking at case studies with the focus on collecting qualitative narratives, including evidence relating to the implementation journey, benefits and disbenefits, outcomes and impacts arising from the implementation of smart technologies in the context of the case study building(s) exemplars received from IEA Annex 81 participants and extended network.

Barriers, incentives, and existing business models for stakeholders' adoption of smart building technologies are also collected to investigate the potential of business model innovation and new smart data-driven strategies to reduce barriers and increase motivation for market adoption. Finally, quantitative information about the case study buildings (e.g., data from the building management system, building plans, etc.) is collected (if possible) and used for demonstration activities of data-driven applications.

Annex participants have identified relevant case studies in their countries and detailed case study leads to fill in a template while given some guidance. We have chosen contributors that have been involved in the decision-making or implementation of one or more smart-building technology solutions. The final version of each case study has been reviewed and approved by the contributor before its publication on the website.

PRIVACY NOTICE

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PROJECT TEAM

GUOKAI CHEN

Guokai Chen is currently a PhD student at the Institute of Environmental Design and Engineering, University College London. Guokai had an engineering background in energy, HVAC system and smart building. He received his bachelor's degree at Tongji University, China and MSc at University College London, UK. He had two-year working experience at Tongji Architecture Design Group in Shanghai as a mechanical engineer in the field of HVAC research and sustainable projects. Guokai is currently working on Subtask D of Annex 81 project, and his PhD research is focusing on control performance on advanced building control strategies such as Model Predictive Control.

VIRGINIA GORI

Dr Virginia Gori is currently a Senior Research Fellow and Lecturer (Teaching) in Building Physics and Engineering at the Bartlett School of Environment, Energy and Resources at the University College London. Virginia has an engineering background, strongly linked to the understanding and assessment of the energy performance of the built environment. After receiving a PhD in Energy and the Built Environment, she was personally awarded an Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) Doctoral Prize Fellowship to fund her post-doctoral research for two years. Virginia is currently working on Subtask D of the IEA Annex 81 project and contributing to its leadership. Virginia's research interests are in the use of data-driven approaches to model and understand the energy performance of the building stock, often with a focus on the potential for retrofit. Her expertise lies at the interface of building physics, in-situ monitoring, and building performance modelling with an aim to provide evidence-based insights for better design and decision-making in the building industry and policy landscape. Virginia is also technical committee member for the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and active member on a number of IEA Annex projects.

PAUL RUYSSSEVELT

Professor Ruysssevelt is a qualified architect with a PhD in superinsulated homes. He is currently Professor of Energy and Building Performance at University College London. He has worked in academia and industry over a 40-year career in sustainable energy, energy efficiency and renewable energy. His research now focuses on understanding energy use in building stocks at the local, city, regional and national levels, and on the performance gap between the reality of energy use in buildings and our expectations or design predictions. He pioneered research into the performance gap issue in 1995 with the creation of the PROBE project which brought the subject to the attention of a mainstream audience for the first time and led to changes in both design practice and regulations. Since joining UCL he has advanced the study of building stocks through the development of SimStock, an epidemiological model of the UK building stock employing dynamic simulation. He now leads research in this field, taking the building stock modelling approach to other regions, with India and Peru being the first of these. Paul maintains an overview of international research through his role as UK ExCo representative to the International Energy Agency programme for Energy in Buildings and Communities which oversees some 20 research projects from 25 member countries.

DIMITRIOS ROVAS

Dr Dimitrios Rovas is currently an Associate Professor in Building Simulation and Optimisation at the Bartlett School of Environment, Energy and Resources at the University College London. Dimitrios received his PhD in Mechanical Engineering from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. He was a research associate at the Laboratory for Numerical Analysis of the University of Paris VI, France (UPMC). He held Assistant Professor positions in the Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, USA, and the Production Engineering and Management Department at the Technical University of Crete, Greece. From 2013 to 2015, he was a member of the Systems Integration Group at the Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics in Germany. His research interests are in building physics, smart buildings, design and simulation of building energy management systems, building simulation, building information modelling and development of middleware and data integration platforms for data access and analytical processing of sensor information. He has developed and led the CIBSE-accredited MSc programme in Smart Buildings and Digital Engineering offered at UCL.

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